

AI Sustainability in Practice

Part One: Foundations for Sustainable AI Projects

What is the AI Ethics and Governance in Practice Programme?

In 2021, the UK's National AI Strategy recommended that UK Government's official Public Sector Guidance on AI Ethics and Safety be transformed into a series of practice-based workbooks. The result is the AI Ethics and Governance in Practice Programme. This series of eight workbooks provides end-to-end guidance on how to apply principles of AI ethics and safety to the design, development, deployment, and maintenance of AI systems. It provides public sector organisations with a Process-Based Governance (PBG) Framework designed to assist AI project teams in ensuring that the AI technologies they build, procure, or use are ethical, safe, and responsible.

At a Glance

Introduces fundamental concepts needed to carry out sustainable AI projects. Presents core governance mechanisms to help AI project teams put AI Sustainability into practice, including:

- The **SUM Values (Respect, Connect, Care, and Protect)**, which support reflection on and assessment of the potential societal impacts and ethical permissibility of AI projects.
- The **Stakeholder Engagement Process (SEP)**, which facilitates proportionate engagement of and input from stakeholders. The **SEP** involves:
 - identifying stakeholders and evaluating their salience (**Stakeholder Analysis**);
 - evaluating team positionality as related to that of stakeholders (**Positionality Reflection**); and
 - establishing **Stakeholder Engagement Objectives and Methods**.

Key Concepts

AI Sustainability

The principle of AI Sustainability ensures that designers and users of AI systems remain aware that these technologies may have transformative effects as well as short-, medium-, and long-term impacts on individuals and society. For AI systems to remain sustainable and support the sustainability of affected communities, AI project teams should proceed with a continuous sensitivity to such real-world effects and impacts.

Stakeholders

Stakeholders are individuals or groups that:

1. have interests or rights that may be affected by the past, present, and future decisions and activities of an organisation;
2. may have the power or authority to influence the outcome of such decisions and activities; and/or
3. have relevant characteristics that put them in positions of advantage or vulnerability with regard to those decisions and activities.

SUM Values

A set of ethical values that provide AI project teams with a shared vocabulary to assess the implications of AI projects and to support, underwrite and motivate responsible innovation practice. Rather than providing comprehensive list, they are meant to be a launching point for collaborative and anticipatory reflection, allowing for the respectful and interculturally sensitive inclusion of other points of view.

Positionality

All individual human beings come from unique places, experiences, and life contexts that shape their thinking and perspectives. Reflecting on this positionality can help people understand how their viewpoints might differ from those around them, especially those who have diverging cultural and socioeconomic backgrounds and life experiences. For AI project teams, such positionality reflection can be essential to ensure the equity in their projects.

Workbook Summary

Sustainable AI projects are continuously responsive to the transformative effects as well as short-, medium-, and long-term impacts on individuals and society that the design, development, and deployment of AI technologies may have. Projects, which centre AI Sustainability, ensure that values-led, collaborative, and anticipatory reflection both guides the assessment of potential social and ethical impacts and steers responsible innovation practices.

This workbook is the first part of a pair that provides the concepts and tools needed to put AI Sustainability into practice. It introduces the SUM Values, which help AI project teams to assess the potential societal impacts and ethical permissibility of their projects. It then presents a Stakeholder Engagement Process (SEP), which provides tools to facilitate proportionate engagement of and input from stakeholders with an emphasis on equitable and meaningful participation and positionality awareness.

The SUM Values

The SUM Values (Respect, Connect, Care, and Protect) are meant to be utilised as guiding values throughout the innovation lifecycle. Adopting common values from the outset enables reciprocally respectful, sincere, and open dialogue about ethical challenges by helping to create a shared vocabulary.

These values, however, are not meant to be comprehensive or fixed. Instead, they are empirically grounded and harms-responsive: They respond to the ethical concerns raised by the set of real-world hazards and risks posed by the use of AI/ML systems:

Risks that Emerge From the Use of AI/ML Technologies	Related Ethical Implications and Concerns	SUM Values
Loss of autonomy	Respect the dignity of individual persons	
Loss of interpersonal connection and empathy	Connect with each other sincerely, openly, and inclusively	
Poor quality or hazardous outcomes	Care for the wellbeing of each and all	
Bias, injustice, inequality, and discrimination	Protect the priorities of social values, justice, and the public interest	

Three Steps of Stakeholder Engagement Process (SEP)

The SEP is a governance process that is comprised of three connected activities:

1. a preliminary project scoping and stakeholder analysis;
2. positionality reflection; and
3. establishment of stakeholder objectives and methods.

The SEP is not a one-off activity, but an ongoing process that occurs throughout the project lifecycle. The initial SEP takes place internally (i.e. within the organisation or team) during the design phase of the project workflow and is informed by available organisational scoping and planning documents and by desk-based research. These resources are used to develop an initial PS Report that is revisited during the Stakeholder Impact Assessment (SIA) and each SIA iteration.

1. Preliminary Project Scoping and Stakeholder Analysis

Outline key project components. Identify individuals or groups who may be affected by, or may affect, your innovation project. Scope potential stakeholder impacts. Evaluate the salience and contextual characteristics of identified stakeholders.

2. Positionality Reflection

Evaluate team positionality as related to that of stakeholders. Consider strengths and limitations presented by team positionality.

3. Stakeholder Engagement Objectives and Methods

Establish engagement objectives that enable the appropriate degree of stakeholder engagement and co-production in project evaluation, and methods that support the achievement of defined objectives.

For detailed information about authorships, acknowledgements, and references, please consult the **AI Sustainability in Practice Part One: Foundations for Sustainable AI Projects** workbook.